

Natural Disaster: Flood and Its Mitigation in Majuli Island

Paper Id : 18584 Submission Date : 10/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 23/02/2024 Publication Date : 25/02/2024
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11063839

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Prasanta Saikia

Assistant Professor
Deptt. Of Geography
Majuli College
Kamalabari, Assam, India

Abstract

Majuli the greatest inhabited riverine island in the world is situated in the northern part of Jorhat District, Assam. The area lies between $26^{\circ} 45' N$ to $27^{\circ} 12' N$ Latitude and $93^{\circ} 39' E$ to $94^{\circ} 35' E$ longitude. The total area of the island is 1256 sq. Km. According to 2011 census it has a population of 167,304 consisting of 85,566 males and 81,738 females, their ratio being 955: 1000.

Keywords Natural Disaster, Flood, Mitigation, Majuli Island.

Introduction

Flood is the only natural disaster that occurs most frequently and repetitively in Majuli. Flood assumes gigantic dimensions because of mighty Brahmaputra river system. The magnitude and frequency of floods are increasing over the years in Majuli. It has been observed that the intensity of floods has increased in the last 200 years (CWC 1994). It causes damages of life and property almost every year, but the enormity varies from year to year.

Aim of study

The main objectives of the study—

- i. To study the cause and effect of the flood.
- ii. To study the flood control measures adopted by the concerning Deptt.
- iii. To study the erosional problems of the Majuli island.

Review of Literature

Flood is a natural phenomenon. Most of the river valley of the world are more or less affected and damaged by flood and erosion. Such a condition different scholars, scientists and research scholars are interested for better understanding and management of such problems for the wellbeing of the society. Flood events as well as their studies and controls have been observed by various countries like China, Egypt, India, Turkey etc. In this research the effect of flood and erosion on flood plain people have also been widely studied. An attempt has been made here to review the literatures on flood and erosion problems, management and its mitigation.

1. Colman, E.A, (1953): His contribution is worth mentioning in the field of floodplain management. His work is prominent relating to the flood plain management and research.

2. Willy, G.R, (1953): His contribution in the field of flood and its associated problems is very specific one. Perhaps he was the path finder regarding the study of flood from the view point of historical perspective.

3. Murphy, P.C, (1958) : He has given importance for the development of new methodology for the assessment of floods and its related problems from the sociological point of view on the one hand and the impact of floods on the people along with human responses on the other.

4. Coleman, J.M. (1969) has worked on the Brahmaputra river from the geological point of view. He has studied well on channel processes and sedimentation of the river Brahmaputra. His work was significant to know the geomorphic characteristics of the river Brahmaputra.
5. Douglas, I. (1973) has worked very significant as he studies on floods as social problem from the view point of behavioral geography and psychology relating to human perspective.
6. Goswami, D.C. (1985) He is known for his specific condition relating to different types of fluvial processes. Most of his works are associated with floodplain of the river Brahmaputra.
7. Nath, D. (1990): He has put forwarded an account of the origin of Majuli. He has explained the socio-economic changes that have been coming gradually to the island.
8. Saikia, N. (1993) has given a geographical interpretation of Majuli in his Ph.D. thesis entitled "Majuli: Geographic study of its problems and prospects". He highlighted the impact of flood on the people of Majuli.
9. Kar, M. (1995) has made a well discussion on flood hazards in his Ph.D. work entitled "Flood Hazards in Nagaon and Marigaon Districts of Assam: A Geographical Perspective". Here he attempts to formulate an appropriate strategy for flood management.
10. Gogoi, B. (1999): In his research work on "Impact of flood in Human occupancies in Sadia Region, Assam". In his studies he tried to analyse the environment affected by flood and erosion of Sadia.
11. Bhattacharjee, N. (2009): In his Ph.D. work entitled "Flood and Bank Erosion problems in Darrang District, Assam: A Fluvio-Geomorphological study" has observed the flood problem of Darrang district seems to be simple apparently the causes, processes involved and resultant landforms.
12. Nath, D. (2009) has written a book entitled "The Majuli island: Society, Economy and Culture". It is indeed a full length monograph on the fascinating Majuli that happens to be a pride of North East and the entire country.
13. Nath, B.K. (2015): In his Ph. D. work entitled "Effects of Flood and Erosion on Socio-Culture and Economic conditions of the people of Majuli sub-division, Jorhat District, Assam"

On the basis of above review of literature it is revealed that there is no similar work has been done so far as the present one relating to Majuli. Therefore, present study is connected not only very singular in nature but also specific one. It is still explored in the field of effects of flood and erosion on the people of Majuli and how to mitigate these problems by the people of Majuli.

Main Text

Significance of the Study:

The present study is assumed to be significant from the following point of view:

The ferocious Brahmaputra criss-crosses the island creating terror not only in the heart of the outsiders, but also among the local inhabitants. There is no man in Majuli who does not pay homage and salutation to the great river when over flowing flood submerges its banks, villages and high *chapories* creating the scenery of a foggy sea where water touches the extreme end of the horizon. Such an area like Majuli has now become more essential as it studies the area in detail and clearly succeeds in finding out the cause and effect of flood and its mitigation. However, as we know, no systematic spatio-temporal analysis of its flood and mitigation and also associated problems has been made. The proposed study is expected to divulge many of the hitherto unknown facts for effective planning and development of the Majuli Island.

Methodology

The present study is done by both inductive and deductive methods. In order to complete, the paper the following methodology has been adopted.

In the first stage, the primary information's are collected from the flood victims of majuli through household survey using schedules and questionnaires. In the second stage, concerning information's are collected from END office, Circle office and office of the Brahmaputra Board, Kamalabari, Majuli. In the third stage, different journals and reference books are taken in to account for necessary information.

The through study has been made on the cause and effect of flood and mitigates the same disaster. Besides, an attempt has also been made to mitigation the disaster and flood control planning and plausible remedies are suggested.

Analysis

Causes of Flood:-

Floods are caused by a number of natural factors as well as anthropogenic activities. The natural factors causing floods in Majuli include:

- i. Prolonged heavy rainfall in the upper stage of the r Brahmaputra River.
- ii. Meandering causes of the river Brahmaputra, Suvansiri, and Lohit.
- iii. Extensive flood plains.
- iv. Break in slope in the long profiles of the rivers.
- v. Blocking of river flows.
- vi. Nature of river valleys and channels.

Anthropogenic activities include:

- i. Channel manipulation through diversion of river course,
- ii. Construction of bridges, barrages and reservoirs,
- iii. Agricultural practice,
- iv. Deforestation in the upper stage of the rivers,
- v. Land use changes.

Flood Control Measures:-

Most of our flood control works aim at minimising the damage caused by floods and protecting as large an area as possible against floods as economically justifiable.

Flood control measures include:

- i. To delay the run off to the rivers,
- ii. To hasten the discharge of water,
- iii. To reduce the volume of water,
- iv. To divert the flow of water ,
- v. To reduce the impact of floods and
- vi. To forewarn the occurrence of floods.

Major Findings:

Flood is the only natural disaster which affect the socio-economic development in the Majuli. Every year flood damages life and property of the region. During rainy season

river Brahmaputra, Suvansiri, and Lohit inundates vast areas of Majuli. The erosional statistics during 1969-2007 was as follows-

i. Erosional statistics during the years 1969-2007

Table No. -1

Rivers	Eroded villages	Eroded area in sq. Km.
Brahmaputra	Salmora, Besamora Mising	0.75
	Kaniajan, Botiamari	0.75
	Sumoimari, Dakhinpat	7.45
	Biri	